

Studies on the Citrate Complex of Beryllium

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The citrate complex of beryllium has been studied in the pH range of 2.6 to 6.0. Beryllium ions react with citric acid and form in the lower pH region a neutral complex (C) liberating two protons according to the reaction :

In the higher pH range this neutral complex dissociates like a dibasic acid to complexes C_1^- and C_2^{2-} according to reactions (ii) and (iii) :

The equilibrium constants of reactions (i), (ii), and (iii) are found to be 4.52×10^{-4} , 2.41×10^{-4} , and 4.95×10^{-6} respectively.

From dialysis studies of Be-Cit system in bicarbonate buffer, Feldman and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4775) found Be^{2+} and citrate ions to combine to form a stable complex at pH 8.25 in maximum molar ratio of 2.

Feldman *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1955, **77**, 878) also studied the same system by ion-exchange method and observed that Be^{2+} did not form any complexes with H_3Cit , but did so with H_2Cit^- , HCit^{2-} , and Cit^{3-} . The instability constants (K) of BeH_2Cit^+ , BeHCit , and BeCit^- are 4×10^{-2} , 6×10^{-3} , and 3×10^{-5} respectively.

From the results obtained above pH 4.0, they have inferred the presence of polynuclear complexes, such as, $\text{Be}_2(\text{HCit})_2$. A complex having a charge more negative than -1 is present above pH 7.0.

EXPERIMENTAL

A very pure sample of beryllium carbonate was dissolved in a known excess of perchloric acid to prevent hydrolysis. The solution was boiled to remove carbon dioxide and then made to 500 c.c.

FIG. 1

The beryllium content was determined by precipitating as hydroxide and then igniting to BeO_2 .

Experiment I.—Curve A (Fig. 1) represents the results obtained by titrating 100 c.c. of the solution containing 0.0015 g. mole of citric acid and 0.025 g. mole of sodium perchlorate against $N/5$ -NaOH at 32° .

Curve B represents the results obtained by titrating the same volume of another solution containing 0.001059 g. mole of beryllium perchlorate (in presence of known excess of perchloric acid which was neutralised by standard alkali before diluting to 100 c.c.), 0.0015 g. mole of citric acid, and 0.025 g. mole of sodium perchlorate against $N/5$ -NaOH at 32° .

Experiment II.—Curve A (Fig. 2) represents results obtained by titrating 100 c.c. of the solution

FIG. 2

containing 0.005 g. mole of citric acid and 0.025 g. mole of sodium perchlorate against $N/5$ -NaOH at 32° .

Curve B represents the results obtained by titrating 100 c.c. of another solution containing 0.005 g. mole of citric acid and 0.001059 g. mole of beryllium perchlorate (in presence of known excess of perchloric acid, which was neutralised by standard alkali before diluting to 100 c.c.) and 0.025 g. mole of sodium perchlorate against $N/5$ -NaOH.

Experiment III.—Curve A (Fig. 3) represents the results obtained by titrating 150 c.c. of a solution containing 0.020 g. mole of sodium citrate and 0.032 g. mole of sodium perchlorate against $0.1N$ -NaOH at 32° .

Curve B represents the results obtained by titrating 150 c.c. of another solution containing 0.001059 g. mole of beryllium perchlorate (in presence of known excess of perchloric acid, which was neutralised by standard alkali before diluting to 100 c.c.), 0.020 g. mole of sodium citrate, and 0.032 g. mole of sodium perchlorate against $0.1N$ -NaOH at 32° .

DISCUSSION

The pH of the system (B) in each case is lower than the corresponding pH in the system (A), indicating the liberation of acid. The horizontal distance between the two curves increases in the beginning and then decreases. The two curves, however, diverge again above pH 6.

In experiment (II), where the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 5, the horizontal distance is very nearly constant. This indicates the formation of a complex with a constant metal to ligand ratio throughout the pH range.

The concentration of the ligand compared to the metal being large, the horizontal distance between the two curves is roughly the measure of the amount of acid liberated. It is therefore found from experiment (II) that one equivalent of acid per atom of Be is liberated. It is therefore very probable that the complex formed contains one ligand per atom of Be.

Calculation of the Equilibrium Constant

The reactions taking place in experiments (I) and (II) are assumed to be similar to that in the citrate complexes of cadmium (Patnaik and Pani, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 673) and may be

represented by equation (1) and the equilibrium constant by equation (1-1).

$$\frac{[\text{C}][\text{H}^+]^n}{[\text{Be}^{2+}][\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]} = K \quad \dots \quad (1-1)$$

By proceeding in a similar manner (Patnaik and Pani, *loc. cit.*) it can be shown that

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[\text{Ct}]}{[\text{C}]} = n - \frac{a}{b}$$

and when the formation of the complex is complete

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[\text{Ct}]}{[\text{Be}(\text{ClO}_4)_2]} = n - \frac{a}{b}$$

$\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$, $-\Delta[\text{Ct}]$, $[\text{Be}(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$, a , and b are calculated as before.

Substituting these values, a series of values of n calculated has been collected in Table I.

TABLE I

pH.	$\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$ $\times 10^3$.	$-\Delta[\text{Ct}]$ $\times 10^4$.	$[\text{Be}(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$ $\times 10^3$.	a/b .	n .	$[\text{C}] \times 10^3$.	$[\text{Be}^{2+}] \times 10^3$.	$[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]$ $\times 10^3$.	$K \times 10^4$.
2.6	5.58	4.2	10.07	0.2560	0.8210	3.261	6.810	8.233	3.670
2.7	6.39	4.8	9.961	0.3046	0.9607	3.856	6.105	7.201	3.491
2.8	8.05	7.1	9.804	0.3588	1.2055	5.085	4.746	5.741	4.663
2.9	9.43	7.1	9.642	0.4184	1.4274	6.148	3.494	4.471	6.237
3.5	12.38	9.3	9.168	0.8351	2.2691				
3.6	12.40	9.4	9.118	0.9078	2.3608				
3.7	12.12	9.0	9.072	0.9797	2.4127				
3.8	11.84	9.0	9.040	1.052	2.466				
3.9	11.72	8.7	8.974	1.127	2.543				
4.0	12.06	9.0	8.935	1.204	2.675				
4.1	11.67	8.7	8.913	1.282	2.716				
4.2	11.57	8.7	8.876	1.362	2.799				
4.3	11.31	8.5	8.839	1.445	2.863				
4.8	10.26	7.7	8.664	1.876	3.227				
5.0	9.65	7.2	8.602	2.049	3.342				
5.2	8.94	6.6	8.545	2.213	3.430				
5.5	8.21	6.2	8.470	2.450	3.599				
5.8	7.53	5.7	8.410	2.653	3.728				
6.0	7.33	5.5	8.375	2.754	3.860				

The values of n gradually increases with pH, but less than 2 in the region below pH 3.2, less than 3 in the region below pH 4.4, and more than 3 but less than 4 above pH 4.5. Below pH 3.2, the complex is formed with the liberation of two protons due to the reaction of beryllium ion and citric acid. Hence the complex is a neutral one. This subsequently dissociates like a dibasic acid in two steps. The reactions are given by equations (2) and (3) and the equilibrium constants are represented by equations (2-1) and (3-1).

$$\frac{[\text{C}_1^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}]} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad (2-1)$$

$$\frac{[C_2^{2-}][H^+]}{[C_1^-]} = K_2 \quad \dots \quad (3-1)$$

K , K_1 , and K_2 are calculated, as determined before, and tabulated in Tables I—III respectively. The mean values of K , K_1 , and K_2 are 4.520×10^{-4} , 2.410×10^{-4} , and 4.95×10^{-6} respectively.

TABLE II

pH.	<i>n</i> -2.	3- <i>n</i> .	$K_1 \times 10^4$.	pH.	<i>n</i> -2.	3- <i>n</i> .	$K_1 \times 10^4$.
3.5	0.2691	0.7309	1.165	4.0	0.675	0.3250	2.077
3.6	0.3608	0.6392	1.418	4.1	0.716	0.2840	2.003
3.7	0.4127	0.5873	1.403	4.2	0.799	0.2010	2.508
3.8	0.4660	0.5340	1.383	4.3	0.863	0.1370	3.157
3.9	0.5430	0.4570	1.496				

TABLE III

pH.	<i>n</i> -3.	4- <i>n</i> .	$K_2 \times 10^6$.	pH.	<i>n</i> -3.	4- <i>n</i> .	$K_2 \times 10^6$.
4.8	0.227	0.773	4.654	5.5	0.599	0.401	4.724
5.0	0.342	0.658	5.198	5.8	0.728	0.272	4.241
5.2	0.430	0.570	4.760	6.0	0.860	0.140	6.124

In experiment (III) (Fig. 3) the curves are similar to those obtained in the case of cadmium citrate and other systems. Here also the curve

FIG. 3

curve B is similar to the neutralisation curve of a strong acid. The pH of the system (B), attained by the addition of 12 c.c. of 0.1 *N*-NaOH, is reached by the system (A) on the addition of only 1 c.c. of NaOH. Hence 11 c.c. of 0.1 *N*-NaOH is consumed by the complex formed from 0.001059 g.mole of beryllium perchlorate.

The liberation of one proton indicates the presence of a beryllium citrate complex having two negative charges (C_2^{2-}).

The structure of the beryllium citrate complexes are just similar to those of the nickel and cadmium citrate already discussed (Patnaik and Pani, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 619).

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